

Surgical Menopause: Are we Pushing Women Towards the Menace of Accelerated Aging and Diseases?

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ABSTRACT

It is a routine practice among gynecologists and general practitioners to recommend hysterectomies for benign gynecological diseases. This article is challenging this practice. **i)** Natural menopause: The reproductive life is divided into 5 stages showing the transition of reproductive function. Discussed the stages of normal reproductive aging in women based on (STRAW +10) 2014. The average age of Menopause is 51 years. Menopausal transitional symptoms occur few years before final natural menopause as changes in the pattern of menstrual cycle, vasomotor hot flushes, night sweats, sleep disturbances, psychological and mental disturbances, somatic symptoms headache, dizziness, palpitations **ii)** Surgical Menopause: Surgical menopause causes severe symptoms due to the sudden fall of estrogen, progesterone, and ovarian androgen. Though ovarian failure develops in 2-5 years after surgery hormone deficiency occurs immediately and symptoms can occur as early as 24-48 hrs. **iii)** Ovarian function after hysterectomy done at a pre-menopausal age: Most likely causes of premature ovarian failure after Hysterectomy where ovaries are conserved a) Interference with ovarian blood supply at the time of surgery. b) Disturbance of Endometrial ovarian relationship c) Deficiency of Uterine Prostaglandins d) Loss of putative reflex pathway from the cervix to the pituitary. **iv)** The appearance of menopausal symptoms. **v)** Difference between Natural Menopause and Surgical Menopause: Surgical menopause with bilateral oophorectomy increases morbidity and is linked to accelerated aging. **vi)** Recommendation for AUB management for benign gynecological disease: Therapeutic Indications of Hysterectomy can be narrowed down to a few life-threatening indications of the ovary, uterus, and cervical malignancies. Prophylactic oophorectomy is done in high-risk BRCA - positive patients.

KEY WORDS: Natural menopause, Surgical Menopause, Ovarian function after hysterectomy done at a pre-menopausal age, appearance of menopausal symptoms, Difference between Natural Menopause and Surgical Menopause, Recommendation for AUB management for benign gynecological disease.

INTRODUCTION:

It is a routine practice among gynecologists to recommend hysterectomy for benign gynecological diseases commonest being fibroid uterus.^[1]

Sapna Desai et al reported in their study done at the low-income setting of Gujrat the incidence of hysterectomy 20.7/1000 year women (95% CI 14.0, 30.8) was considered higher than in other countries at a low mean age of 36 years.^[2]

After completing the reproductive function the attitude among women towards the uterus special from

low-income and low-education backgrounds is as the uterus is not needed any more.

It is better to get it removed. Hence for benign gynecological complaints at the early age of 30 and 40 decades, they opt for hysterectomies without being aware of its potential long-term health hazards.^[3] Young enthusiastic doctors perform hysterectomies to gain perfection over their surgical skills.^[2]

Through this article, I will discuss the various aspects of Natural and Surgical Menopause, the risks of early surgical menopause, and conservative treatment options for the benign gynecological disease.

Natural Menopause :

Natural menopause occurred as described by the stages of the reproductive aging workshop (STRAW) in 2001. The reproductive life is divided into 5 stages showing the transition of reproductive function^[4]. The 2011 STRAW+10 workshop reviewed

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advances in the understanding of the critical changes in hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian function that occur before and after the final menstrual period (FMP).^[5] STRAW+10 simplified bleeding criteria for the early and late menopausal transition, recommended modifications to criteria for the late reproductive stage (Stage-3) and the early post-menopause stage (Stage +1), provided information on the duration of the late transition (Stage-1) and early post-menopause (Stage +1) and recommended application regardless of women's age, ethnicity, body size or lifestyle characteristics.

Early Menopausal Transition (Stage-2):

During the early menopausal transition period menstrual cycle length has increased variability, defined as a persistent difference of ≤ 7 days in the length of consecutive cycles. Persistence is defined as recurrence within 10 cycles of the first variable length cycle. Cycles in the early menopausal transition also have variable FSH levels and low AMH levels and AFC.

Late Menopausal Transition (Stage-1):

The late menopausal transition is marked by the occurrence of amenorrhea of 60 days or longer. Menstrual cycles in the late menopausal transition are characterized by variability in cycle length, extreme fluctuations in hormonal levels, and frequent anovulation. AMH levels fall and become undetectable levels. FSH levels > 25 IU/L is criteria which indicate a late transition, this stage is estimated to last on average 1-3 years. Symptoms, most notably vasomotor symptoms, are likely to occur during this stage.

EARLYPOSTMENOPAUSE (Stage+1a, +1b, +1c):

FSH continues to increase and estradiol continues to decrease until approximately two years after the Final Menopause Period (FMP), after which levels of each of these hormones stabilize. Thus, STRAW +10 recommended that Early Post Menopause be subdivided into 3 substages (+1a, +1b, and +1c).

Stages +1a and +1b each last one year and end at the time point at which FSH and estradiol levels stabilize. Stage +1a marks the end of the 12-month period of amenorrhea required to define that the FMP has occurred. It corresponds to the end of the 'perimenopause', a term still in common usage that means the time around the menopause and begins at Stage -2 and ends 12 months after the FMP. Stage +1b includes the remainder of the period of rapid changes in

mean FSH and estradiol levels. Based on studies of hormonal changes, Stages +1a, and +1b together are estimated to last on average 2 years. Symptoms, most notably vasomotor symptoms, are most likely to occur during this stage. Stage +1c represents the period of stabilization of high FSH levels and low estradiol values that is estimated to last 3 to 6 years, thus the entire early post-menopause lasts approximately 5-8 years. Further specification of this stage will require additional studies of trajectories of change in FSH and estradiol from the FMP through the late post-menopause.

Late postmenopause (stage +2):

Stage +2 represents the period in which further changes in reproductive endocrine function are more limited and processes of somatic aging take precedence. Vaginal dryness and urogenital atrophy become the leading symptoms. However, mean FSH levels fall again many years after menopause in the very elderly⁷⁰.

Hysterectomy And Endometrial Ablation:

Women in whom hysterectomy or endometrial ablation is done. They cannot be staged by menstrual bleeding criteria. Reproductive stage in these women can be assessed only by the supportive criteria of ovarian biomarkers. It is recommended to wait for minimum 3 months post surgery to assess endocrine status given emerging evidence that pelvic surgeries may transiently raise FSH levels.

The average age of Menopause is 51 years^[9] Menopause Transitional Symptoms occurring few years before final natural menopause are:

- 1) There is a change in the pattern of the menstrual cycle. The duration of the cycle becomes either longer or shorter irregular acyclical or inter-menstrual spotting.
- 2) Vasomotor hot flushes, night sweats, sleep disturbances.
- 3) Psychological and mental disturbances -worsening pre-menstrual syndrome, depression, irritability mood swings, loss of concentration, poor memory, vaginal dryness, decreased libido painful intercourse (dyspareunia).
- 4) Somatic symptoms -headache, dizziness, palpitations, breast pain, enlargement, joint aches and back pain, urinary complaints-incontinence, weight gain

SURGICAL MENOPAUSE:

Surgical menopause occurs when ovaries are surgically removed in a pre-menopausal woman

Stages of normal reproductive aging in women (STRAW +10):

Stages	-5	-4	-3b	-3a	-2	-1	+1a	+1b	+1c	+2
Terminology	Reproductive				Menopausal Transition		Post menopause			
Duration	Early	Peak	Late		Early	Late	Early			Late
					Perimenopausal					
	Variable duration				Variable	1-3 yrs	1 yr	1yr	3-6 yrs yr	Remaining life
Principle criteria										
Menstrual cycle	regular to variable	Regular	Regular	Subtle change in flow/length	Variable length of cycle > 7 days difference in length of consecutive cycles	Skipped cycles and interval of amenorrhea >60 days	Amenorrhea			
Supportive criteria										
Endocrinal criteria FSH AMH Inhibin B			Normal Low Low	Variable Low Low	Variable Low Low	Variable >25IU/L Low Low	Variable Low Low	Stabilize Very Low Very Low		
Antral Follicle Count 2-10 mm			Low	Low	Low	Low	Very Low		Very Low	
Descriptive characteristics										
Symptoms							Vasomotor symptoms likely	Vasomotor symptoms Most likely		Increasing symptoms of Uro genital atrophy

causing an abrupt endocrine deficient state. Surgical menopause causes severe symptoms due to the sudden fall of estrogen, progesterone, and ovarian androgen.

In postmenopausal women, the ovary does not stop its function completely. It contributes to 50% of the testosterone and 30% of androstenedione. These androgens are converted peripherally to estrogen. The incidence of ovarian failure is 25-57% in women who have undergone hysterectomy alone. Though ovarian failure develops in 2-5 years after surgery, hormone deficiency occurs immediately and symptoms can occur as early as 24-48 hrs. The explainable reason is ovarian blood supply is affected post-surgery.

Patricia G. Moorman et al studied the increased risk of earlier ovarian failure is a possible consequence of Premenopausal hysterectomy.^[6]

Emanuel C. Trabuco et al studied Women undergoing hysterectomy who had similar antimüllerian hormone levels at baseline and experienced a greater percent decrease in levels after 1 year compared with referents, suggesting that hysterectomy may lead to ovarian damage that is unrelated to baseline ovarian reserve.^[7]

S. Muttukrishna et al in a study showed that ovarian inhibin A and B were cleared from the circulation within 12 hours of oophorectomy, whereas E2 and progesterone remain in the circulation for longer. A negative correlation between FSH, inhibin A, and inhibin B suggests that inhibins may contribute to the observed early rise in FSH after surgical

menopause.^[8]

William H. Parker et al reported that for women younger than 50 at the time of hysterectomy, bilateral oophorectomy was associated with significantly increased mortality in women who had never used estrogen therapy. At no age was oophorectomy associated with increased overall survival.^[9]

Causes of Premature ovarian failure after Hysterectomy where ovaries are conserved:

- i) Interference with ovarian blood supply at the time of surgery.
- ii) Disturbance of Endometrial ovarian relationship
- iii) Deficiency of Uterine Prostaglandins
- iv) Loss of putative reflex pathway from the cervix to pituitary.

Surgical menopause occurs when ovaries are removed in pre-menopausal women causing an abrupt endocrine deficiency.

- I) Surgical removal of pathological or normal of one or both ovaries.
- ii) Hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy
- iii) Abdominal resection for colorectal cancer
- iv) Pelvic exenteration in carcinoma cervix
- v) Radiotherapy or chemotherapy-induced menopause
- vi) While performing Uterine artery embolization

few polyvinyl particles go to the ovarian artery and its blood supply is affected.

Comparison between surgical menopause and natural menopause:

- I During surgical menopause vasomotor symptoms appear immediately and symptoms are more intense and last for more duration. Almost 90% of women with surgical menopause have these symptoms. They require high doses of estrogen and even testosterone to relieve the symptoms. They have a high chance of recurrence after the stoppage of treatment. In natural menopause, the vasomotor symptoms (VMS) is slow and starts gradually, which is less intense and for a short duration. Only 50% of women suffer from these symptoms. They respond to a low dose of estrogen and do not require testosterone. They have less chance of recurrence.
- ii) Psychological well-being and sexuality improved as the disease is treated significant loss of libido hormone therapy (HT) shows improvement. Testosterone or Tibolone is added. In natural menopause, the woman may be depressed and have anxiety disorder, no sudden change but reduced interest is due to vaginal dryness and painful coitus, HT shows improvement
- iii) Cardio Vascular Heart Disease (CHD)- Significant atherosclerosis, there is more chance of CHD. Early ET is cardioprotective less chance of CHD. ET is not recommended for cardio-protection.^[10]
- iv) BMD and fracture risk: in surgical menopause rapid and high incidence of osteoporosis and fracture due to rapid bone loss. Estrogen therapy (ET) shows improvement. Early initiation of ET to prevent symptoms. The dose is inversely proportional to age and continued till natural menopause

Natural menopause bone loss follows an exponential pattern 4-5 yrs after menopause (vertebral common), and ET fails to improve. Estrogen Progesterone Testosterone Replacement (E+P+T) for endometrial protection and symptoms. The smallest effective dose for the shortest possible time. Tailoring the dose as individualized for symptoms relief within 10 yrs of menopause.

Thus surgical menopause with bilateral oophorectomy increases morbidity and is linked to accelerated aging.^[11]

Thus it is better to conserve ovaries before natural menopause as its removal carries a high morbidity. Hysterectomy should be done only when other methods fail and oophorectomy should be

avoided. Meticulous efforts should be made to conserve the blood supply of ovaries.

Indian Menopause Society Clinical practice guidelines on menopause in 2013 have suggested evidence-based good clinical practice guidelines in the Indian perspective on the management of Abnormal Uterine Bleeding in a reproductive period which is the commonest indication for hysterectomy.^[12]

Polyp -hysteroscopic surgical removal of multiple polyps or polypoidal endometrium and fertility is not desired then LNG IUS can be combined with surgical removal.

Adenomyosis -LNG IUS, if LNG IUS is not accepted then GnRH agonist with Add back therapy, if it fails or is contraindicated then OCP, NSAIDS, and Progestogens for symptom relief. Conservative surgery (adenomyomectomy) in selected cases. A hysterectomy is the last resort.

Leiomyoma: Intramural or subserosal myoma (grade 2 to 6). Tranexamic acid or COC or NSAIDS, LNG-IUS, if treatment fails then myomectomy depends on location.

In women age >40 yrs of age, fertility is not desired for small fibroids (4-5 cms) medical management is followed by a hysterectomy.

Short term management -(up to 6 months) GnRH agonist with add-back therapy followed by myomectomy.

Long-term management-LNG IUS Newer treatment options - Progesterone receptor modulator - Ulipristal acetate or low dose mifepristone. Submucosal myomectomy (grade 0-1) hysteroscopy (<4cm) or abdomen or open route if >4cm

Malignancy- Atypical endometrial hyperplasia treatment is surgical if fertility is not desired then hysterectomy. Hyperplasia without atypia LNG IUS alternatively progestins.

COEIN -LNG IUS or Tranexamic Acid, NSAIDS, COCs, or cyclical oral progestins (D5 - 25) Luteal Phase Progestins (D 15 -25) only in AUB - O. Medical or surgical treatment failed or contraindicated GnRH agonists with add-back therapy. When steroidal and other options are not suitable consider Centchroman.

CONCLUSION:

So the Therapeutic Indications of Hysterectomy can be narrowed down to a few life-threatening indications.

- I Endometrial malignancy
- ii) Ovarian malignancy
- iii) Early invasive cancer cervix
- iv) Ovarian involvement complex-ovarian

cyst, endometriosis, chronic pelvic infection (PID).

- v) Prophylactic oophorectomy is done in high-risk BRCA - positive patients for breast or ovarian cancer

Thus limiting hysterectomy to only serious indications can save women from many potential diseases.

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